

**VLADIMIR PAVLOVICH BOBIN – A DOCTOR
AND SOCIAL ACTIVIST OF KHARKIV
MEDICAL SOCIETY
(DEDICATED TO HIS 160-YEAR
ANNIVERSARY)**

**Bobina I. V., Lutenko M. A., Andreyev G. I.,
Popov N. N., Davydenko M. B.**

The Kharkiv Medical Society (KhMS) was founded in 1861 due to the initiative of the Kharkov University Medical Faculty professors Grube V. F., Ryndovsky G. S., and doctor Frankovsky V. F. It was one of the first scientific and practical societies of doctors in Russia. There were prominent scientists and doctors among its 26 founders, including university professors. Besides Kharkov doctors, scientists that have earned worldwide fame were selected as the honorary members of the KhMS — R. Virchow, L. Paster, I. Lister, R. Koch,

G. Helmholtz, A. Ya. Krasovskiy, and others. The society has founded several institutions important for that time – Bacteriological Station, Pasteur Institute, a number of specialized hospitals and clinics, including a hospital and clinic for out-patients. All institutions were providing free help to the patients.

One of the most active participants of KhMS was Vladimir Pavlovich Bobin – the doctor administrator of the clinic and the hospital. Vladimir Pavlovich was born in 11 July, 1858 in Pereyaslavl in the family of the Theology Master. Then the family moved to Kharkiv. V. P. Bobin has received middle school education in the 3rd Kharkoiv gimnasium. In 1881, Vladimir Pavlovich has graduated from the medical department of Kharkov University, then worked at the department of general pathology under the management of prof. I. N. Obolensky.

Fig 1. The group of students of the Kharkov University Medical Department (Vladimir Pavlovich is sitting in the first row, second to the left, 1881).

Due to his active disposition, Vladimir Pavlovich wanted to test himself in practice and starting from November, 1884 began to work as a doctor-administrator in the clinic, and less than a year afterwards has also started working in the same position at the KhMS hospital located on Pushkinskaya, 14. He has been managing this hospital for 43 years. The clinic and the hospital founded by Kharkov doctors and activists: Grube V. F., Kuznetsov A. Kh., Frankovskiy V. F., Zarubin I. K. and others not only helped the citizens of Kharkiv and the governorate, but in fact all of the Left Coast Ukraine and the nearby Russian provinces. The

clinic was one of the first and oldest establishment founded by the Society. There was a center for emergency medical assistance in the clinic, initiated by Vladimir Pavlovich. The flat of V. P. Bobin was situated near the hospital, and he used to give first aid to the patients day and night. In his report on the 25 activity of the hospital (1910 г.), Vladimir Pavlovich pointed out: *«But our predominant and most important advantage that our hospital is rightfully proud of is the fact that it accepts patients independent of any kind of conditions, such as place of residence, class, religion, etc. In other words, it aims to satisfy the needs of the patient first».*

Fig 2.V.P. Bobin, 1888

Year after year, the quantity of patients coming to the hospital was growing. There were in average 11-13 thousand patients treated every year at the time. And they were mainly the poorest – the workers and farmers of the Kharkov and other provinces. The KhMS hospital had a therapeutic and surgical departments, as well as several maternity beds; mostly patients in serious conditions came to the hospital - those with traumas, injuries, as well as diseases of the digestive tract, respiratory diseases, circulatory and infectious conditions. Besides conducting treatments, the doctors at the hospital organized scientific conferences that attracted not only practicing surgeons, but also clinical professors from Kharkov University.

In his memoirs, V. P. Bobin's son, Victor Vladimirovich, wrote: «*Father was a therapist by specialization, but possessed enormous knowledge in many areas of medicine, and in his notes and medical calendars one could constantly find the abstracts of the news from local and foreign journals*».

The activities of V. P. Bobin were multi-faceted, as he was active not only as a doctor, but as a social activist as well. In the years 1910–1912, he was the manager of the building board of KhMS and was working on creation of the “Palace of Medicine” together with the

architect A. N. Beketov. Now this building is widely known in our country and abroad as the SE “Mechnikov Institute of Microbiology and Immunology of NAMS of Ukraine». He was the head of the beneficiary council of the Alexandrov hospital, has persuaded the state Duma to allocate funds for the building of the gynecology department, and was himself the executive leader of the latter enterprise. In 1892, based on his proposal, a branch of St. Petersburg Society for Mutual Aid was opened in Kharkov. For many years, V. P. Bobin worked as a school doctor at the 3rd Kharkov gymnasium and with his work has shown how important the role of school doctor is. Together with his brother, Pavel Pavlovich, he was studying the efficacy of Berezovsky mineral waters and proved the importance of their application in treatment of many diseases. The courageous, selfless work of V. P. Bobin, his sensitive, attentive treatment of people, crystal clear honesty and active participation in various projects has earned him deep respect, appreciation and love both from medical professionals and wide citizen circles. In 1906, when medical society of Kharkov has celebrated his 25 anniversary of his work as a doctor, KhMS has elected him as their honorary member, and one of the beds in the hospital was given his name.

Fig 3. The middle part of the main facade of the new building of the Medical Society, 1912

In the speech addressed to the man of the hour, it was stated: «As doctor-administrator of the free clinic and hospital of KhMS, you have accumulated wide popularity among the poorest citizens of Kharkiv due to your medical experience, knowledge, sensitive and humane treatment of patients». After the October revolution, Vladimir Pavlovich continued managing the hospital of medical society that was reassigned as the Protozoan Institute hospital in 1923. The People's Commissar of the Inspection of Workers and Farmers assigned to him the evaluation of the medical establishment of the city. The committee under his leadership has introduced a number of proposals, that led to the improvements of public health service in Kharkov.

Vladimir Pavlovich Bobin has died on 11 November, 1925 after a difficult illness. The Management of KhMS in their letter to the Health Committee of Ukraine has noted that V. P. Bobin «was known for his selfless and humane work far beyond the Ukrainian borders, his name was a symbol of highest honesty, responsibility to his work as a doctor, attentive and loving treatment of working patients».

On the facade of the SE “Mechnikov Institute for Microbiology and Immunology of NAMNS of Ukraine», where Vladimir Pavlovich used to live and work, one can see memorial panels dedicated to this wonderful doctor, talented clinician, health protection organizer and social activist — Vladimir Pavlovich Bobin.

Fig 4. Facade of the SE “Mechnikov Institute for Microbiology and Immunology of NAMNS of Ukraine»